

Psychological Safety - Pilot

Survey Flow

Standard: Welcome page (1 Question)
Standard: Prolific (1 Question)
Standard: Screening Questions (5 Questions)
Standard: Demographic (9 Questions)
Standard: Project and Team (11 Questions)
Standard: Measuring psychological safety (3 Questions)
Standard: Antecedents of Psychological Safety - Leadership (6 Questions)
Standard: Antecedents of Psychological Safety - Team (3 Questions)
Standard: Antecedents of Psychological Safety - Team 2 (3 Questions)
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Standard: Effect of Psychological Safety (10 Questions)
Standard: Moderating variables (4 Questions)

Page Break

Start of Block: Welcome page

WP

Thanks for taking time to participate in our survey.

In this research project, we aim at understanding agile teams approaches to admitting mistakes, taking initiatives, talking about problems, and helping each other and how doing so contributes to achieving software quality. Your participation is anonymous, and the survey should take 15 mins to complete.

This research project is led by Adam Alami, assistant professor at Aalborg University, Denmark, in collaboration with Mansooreh Zahedi, assistant professor at the University of Melbourne and Oliver Krancher, associate professor at the IT University of Copenhagen, Denmark.

Your data will be used to carry out research for scholarly publication. As part of the publication process, the data will be shared in anonymized form, which does not reveal the identity of the survey participants and their organisations.

We thank you again for helping us to understand better how agile teams help each other and work collaboratively to achieve better software quality.

Sincerely,

Adam Alami, Mansooreh Zahedi and Oliver Krancher

Page Break

End of Block: Welcome page

Start of Block: Prolific

Q66 What is your Prolific ID?

End of Block: Prolific

Start of Block: Screening Questions

SQ1 Are you currently working in an agile software development team?

No

Yes

SQ2 Do your tasks in your team include software development, leading a software development team, software architecting, quality assurance (QA) tasks or leading a QA team?

Yes

No

SQ3 How many years of experience do you have working as a software developer or quality assurance analyst or engineer?

Less than 5 years

More than 5 years

SQ4 Where are you currently located?

▼ United States ... Other

P1 Can you please share your feedback, if any of last questions are unclear?

Page Break

End of Block: Screening Questions

Start of Block: Demographic

DM1 What is your age?

- 30 years or younger
 - 31 - 40 years
 - 41 - 50 years
 - Over 51 years old
-

DM2 How do you identify your gender?

- Male
 - Female
 - Non-binary / third gender
 - Prefer not to say
 - Prefer to self-describe (please specify below)
-

P2 Can you please share your feedback, if any of the last questions are unclear?

DM3 What is your role in your software development team?

- Software engineer
- Senior software engineer
- Tech Lead
- Solution architect
- Quality assurance engineer
- Quality assurance analyst
- QA Lead
- Other (please specify below)

DM4 How many years of your experience has in software development and/or quality assurance?

- 3 - 5 years
- 6 - 8 years
- 9 - 11 years
- More than 12 years

P3 Can you please share your feedback, if any of the last questions are unclear?

Page Break

DM5 How many years of your experience has been in agile teams?

- Less than 3 years
 - 3 - 5 years
 - 6 - 8 years
 - 9 - 11 years
 - More than 12 years
-

DM6 What is your education level?

- Bachelor's degree
 - Master's degree
 - PhD
 - Other (please specify below)
-

P4 Can you please share your feedback, if any of the last questions are unclear?

Page Break

End of Block: Demographic

Start of Block: Project and Team

PT1 Throughout this survey, we will be asking questions regarding your current team. In all questions, we use "team", "my team" or "our team" to refer to your current team. Please, answer all the questions in the context of your current team. Do you understand this requirement?

- Yes, I understand this requirement
- No, I do not understand this requirement

Page Break

PT2 What agile method do you use in your team?

- Scrum
 - XP
 - Kanban
 - SAFe
 - Other (please specify below)
-

PT3 How many people are on your team?

PT4 To what extent to you agree with the following statement:

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
In my team, we have people with all the skills (e.g., front-end, back-end, database, operations, business users) that are required for the project	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

PT5 What type of product/software do you develop in your team?

- Custom development
 - Implementation of software packages/COTS
 - Maintenance/enhancement of existing system(s)
 - Other (specify below) _____
-

PT6 How long has your team been working together?

- Less than 1 year
 - 1 – 2 years
 - 3 – 4 years
 - More than 4 years
-

P5 Can you please share your feedback, if any of the last questions are unclear?

Page Break _____

PT7 Are you an in-house software team (i.e., you develop software for your own organisation) or an outsourced software team (i.e., you develop software for client that is another organisation)?

- In-house
 - Outsourced
 - Other (specify below) _____
-

PT8 How often are the members of your team colocated?

- Always
 - 3-4 days per week
 - 1-2 days per week
 - Less than 1 day per week
-

PT9 Do you work in a project that involves multiple teams?

- No
 - Yes
-

P6 Can you please share your feedback, if any of the last questions are unclear?

Page Break

End of Block: Project and Team

Start of Block: Measuring psychological safety

PS2 Throughout this survey we will use the term psychological safety. It means that in your work environment you believe and feel it is ok to admit mistakes and report them, you believe and feel it is ok and acceptable to report and discuss difficult problems, you are welcomed to propose initiatives and discuss them with your team and you feel at ease to ask for help when you need it. I have read and understand this definition.

Yes

No

Page Break

PS1 To what extent do you agree with these statements:

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
If you make mistakes on my team, is it often held against you	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Members of my team can bring up problems and tough issues	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
People on my team sometimes reject others for being different	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
It is safe to take a risk (e.g., experiment with a new technology, propose initiatives, raise an issue, disclose own knowledge gaps) on my team	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
It is difficult to ask other members of my team for help	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
No one on my team would deliberately act in a way that undermine my efforts	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Working with members of my team, my unique skills and talents are valued and utilized

P7 Can you please share your feedback, if any of the last questions are unclear?

Page Break

Start of Block: Antecedents of Psychological Safety - Leadership

RQ1.1 To what extent do you agree with these statements:

Our leadership ...	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
... is resolute about psychological safety in our team	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... is determined to promote a work environment where people dare to take risks	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... accepts that failure can occur when we try out new things	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Page Break

RQ1.2 To what extent do you agree with these statements:

Our leadership ...	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
... listens to our needs	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... wants to hear about our concerns	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... is willing to listen to our suggestions	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

P8 Can you please share your feedback, if any of the last questions are unclear?

Page Break

RQ1.3 To what extent do you agree with these statements:

Our leadership ...	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
... is supportive of us	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... provides help with everything we need to deliver our current project	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... treats us with respect	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... supports us doing our work	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Page Break

RQ1.4 To what extent do you agree with these statements:

Our leadership ...	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
... “walk the talk” when it comes to taking risk and accepting failure	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... “practice what they preach” when it comes to psychological safety	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... follows through on the values of psychological safety	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... are role models in terms of taking risks and accepting failures	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... words are well aligned with their actions when it comes to admitting mistakes	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

P9 Can you please share your feedback, if any of the last questions are unclear?

Page Break

End of Block: Antecedents of Psychological Safety - Leadership

Start of Block: Antecedents of Psychological Safety - Team

RQ1.5 To what extent do you agree with these statements:

In our team ...	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
... we are responsible for deciding how to organize our work	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... we decide how to achieve our goals	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... we make the decisions regarding the technical solutions with no interferences from management or our stakeholders	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... we make the decisions regarding the tasks' estimation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... we make the decisions for changing our work processes in order to improve our performance	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... we have the freedom to make decisions on architectural design	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

decisions,
choice of
technology
and tools

Page Break

RQ1.6 To what extent do you agree with these statements:

In our team ...	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
... we engage in constructive discussions to make our decisions	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... each team member's voice counts when decisions are made	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... we make decisions based on the best arguments that team members contribute	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... we aim to reach consensus when we make our decisions	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

P10 Can you please share your feedback, if any of the last questions are unclear?

Page Break

RQ1.7 To what extent do you agree with this statement:

In our team, we have ...	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
... uncommitted time that we can use for activities beyond developing new functionality	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... have enough time available to ensure we can meet deadlines even if something goes wrong	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... have no problems obtaining sufficient time for activities that do not immediately produce customer value	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

RQ1.8 Our use of engineering practices (e.g., test automation, continuous integration) ...

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
... reduces the likelihood that something goes wrong	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... gives us the confidence that we can change code without breaking the software	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... makes us confident that we notice mistakes before they turn into big problems	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

P11 Can you please share your feedback, if any of the last questions are unclear?

Page Break

End of Block: Antecedents of Psychological Safety - Team 2

Start of Block: Antecedents of Psychological Safety - Leadership and Team

RQ1.9 To what extent do you agree with these statements:

In our team ...	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
... we do not blame each other for mistakes but see them as an opportunity for improvement	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... we do not blame each other for underperforming, instead we coach each other to improve	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Our leadership, including team leader and middle management, do not blame individuals for mistakes	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

End of Block: Antecedents of Psychological Safety - Leadership and Team

Start of Block: Antecedents of Psychological Safety - Individuals 1

RQ1.10 To what extent do you agree with these statements:

People in our team ...

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
... are open to criticism and feedback from their peers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... welcome new ideas and initiatives put forward by their peers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... do not reject ideas based on the individual who proposed it but based on the strength and the soundness of the idea	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... accept the rejection of new ideas when the rejection is based on strong arguments	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... accept the rejection of ideas when they fail to convince team members with their arguments	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

P12 Can you please share your feedback, if any of the last questions are unclear?

Page Break

RQ1.11 To what extent do you agree with these statements:

In my team ...

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
... people raise their concerns	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... people talk about problems	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... people share their opinions	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... people point out quality problems	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

P13 Can you please share your feedback, if any of the last questions are unclear?

Page Break

Start of Block: Software Quality

SWQ.1 Throughout this survey we will be asking questions related to software quality. We use ISO/IEC 25010 definition of software quality, which states: “[Software quality is] the degree to which the system satisfies the stated and implied needs of its various stakeholders, and thus provides value”. This ISO model also covers some non-functional characteristics, mainly, “performance”, “compatibility”, “usability”, “reliability”, “security”, “maintainability”, and “portability.” Do you agree with this definition?

- Strongly disagree
 - Somewhat disagree
 - Neither agree nor disagree
 - Somewhat agree
 - Strongly agree
-

SWQ.2 Would you like to comment on your answer?

P14 Can you please share your feedback, if any of the last questions are unclear?

Page Break

SWQ.3 To what extent do you agree with this statement:

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
Our software satisfies the stated needs of its various stakeholders	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Our software satisfies the implied needs of its various stakeholders	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Our software provides value to its stakeholders	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Our software meets the non-functional requirements that are important for its stakeholders	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

SWQ.4 Are there any other software quality attributes your software fulfils?

P15 Can you please share your feedback, if any of the last questions are unclear?

Page Break

End of Block: Software Quality

Start of Block: Effect of Psychological Safety

RQ2.1 To what extent do you agree with this statement:

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
Members of my team admit mistakes related to software quality	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Members of my team do not get blamed by their team members for mistakes related to software quality	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I admit my mistakes related to software quality to my team because there are no repercussions, instead we deal with the situation constructively	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
When mistakes related to software quality are admitted by a team member, we deal with the situation constructively	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

RQ2.2 What type of mistakes related to software quality have you experienced and admitted to your team in the past? Can you share two examples?

P16 Can you please share your feedback, if any of the last questions are unclear?

Page Break

RQ2.3 To what extent do you agree with this statement:

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
As a team, when we admit mistakes, we learn from our mistakes	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Past mistakes usually become a point of reference in our team	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
When past mistakes become a point of reference in our team, we avoid similar mistakes in the future	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Page Break

RQ2.4 To what extent do you agree with this statement:

In my team ...	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
... we understand that we need to help each other	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... we often help each other on software quality related issues	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... we often ask for help from our peers to improve the quality of code when needed	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... we often ask for help from our peers to resolve defects when needed	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... we share knowledge related to software quality to help each other to improve the quality of our work when needed	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

P17 Can you please share your feedback, if any of the last questions are unclear?

Page Break

RQ2.5 To what extent do you agree with this statement:

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
As a team, we collectively solve problems when needed	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
When there are tough problems to solve in our team, we analyze them jointly	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
As a team, we help each other to solve software quality problems (e.g., resolving defects, making design decisions, coding decisions) when needed	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Page Break

RQ2.6 To what extent do you agree with this statement:

In my team ...

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
... we often propose software quality initiatives	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... we often propose software quality-related experiments	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... we often try out new things to increase software quality	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... prior to experimenting with new ideas, we collectively assess the potential risks to help us decide	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Members of my team often make suggestions for improving software quality	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

RQ2.6 What type of experiments and initiatives related to software quality have you taken in your team in the past? Can you share two examples?

P18 Can you please share your feedback, if any of the last questions are unclear?

Page Break

End of Block: Effect of Psychological Safety

Start of Block: Moderating variables

RQ3.2 In your team, how often do you coach each other on software quality related issues?

- Never
 - Sometimes
 - About half the time
 - Most of the time
 - Always
-

RQ3.1 In your team, how often do you use pair programming to help each other?

- Never
 - Sometimes
 - About half the time
 - Most of the time
 - Always
-

P19 Can you please share your feedback, if any of the last questions are unclear?

P20 Thank you for taking the time to complete this survey. We truly value the information you have provided. Your responses will contribute to our research and further our understanding of how a psychologically safe workplace helps software development teams to achieve higher software quality.

Many thanks,
Adam Alami, Mansooreh Zahedi and Oliver Krancher

End of Block: Moderating variables
